

TERRITORIAL- ADMINISTRATIVE DIVISION OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF PRIZREN FROM 1945 TO THE PRESENT

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ABSTRACT

The administrative division of the municipality of Prizren and the change of the border of this municipality from a scientific aspect has not been adequately addressed so far. The evaluation system is addressed in all documentation and others that directly or indirectly provide us with information about the administrative division and the evolution over the years of the territory. This paper aims to present chronologically the administrative division and the evolution over the years of the administrative division of the municipality of Prizren and in tabular and cartographic ways of the creation materials. For the drafting of the paper, research methods based on contemporary methodology will be used. We have more in some comparative to find the differences in the administrative extension of the region over the years, while some of the cartographic will illustrate some of the results found in this analysis.

Keywords: Administrative division, evolution, municipality of Prizren, territory, settlement, borders.

1. INTRODUCTION

The territory of the present-day municipality of Prizren was inhabited by the Illyrians, namely the Dardanian tribe, since ancient times. Before the Roman conquests, the territory of Prizren was part of the Dardanian Kingdom as an independent cultural, religious and political community. In terms of administrative territory, Dardania, which was established in the 4th century BC, included a fairly large area, present-day Kosovo and other surrounding regions. Its borders extended to the city of Niš in the north, and to the south to Kukës and the upper reaches of the Vardar.¹ The Albanian lands initially fell under Roman, respectively Byzantine, then for a time Bulgarian rule, in the 12th century they were conquered by the Slavs. Stefan Nemanja expanded his power to most of the Albanian lands. Stefan Dushan during the 13th century included most of the Albanian lands in his Empire.

The Ottomans penetrated Kosovo in 1389, where the Battle of Kosovo took place. After conquering most of the present-day territory of Kosovo, in 1455 they formed a territorial and administrative unit, which they baptized with the name "Vëllk Vilayet", after the ruler of the pre-Ottoman conquest, Vuk Branković.

¹ History of the Albanian People, Institute of History, Prishtina 1999, p.26

The Vilayet of Vëllk was transformed into a sandžak during the reign of Sultan Mehmet II and is known as the Sandžak of Vushtri.² Based on the source data known so far, it appears that the present-day territory of Prizren in the 15th and 16th centuries was administratively part of the Sandzak of Prizren.³ Prizren again secured an important role as the seat of the vilayet based on the law of 1864, which approved the Law on vilayets, and in 1868 a new reorganization took place, so the Vilayet of Prizren was formed with its seat in Prizren. This Vilayet was divided into four sandjaks: Prizren, Skopje, Dibra and Niš, when a wide territory from Elbasan, Mat and Dibra, across the Lume e Gusi, to the Peja region was placed under its jurisdiction, then to Dukagjini, Kosovo, Skopje, Tetovo, Gostivar, most of Eastern Macedonia, and in the north Vranje, Leskovci, Niš, Prokuplje and Kušumlija. After the peace treaty in Berlin, Prizren lost the function of the vilayet center. Later, with the reforms of 1877, the Vilayet of Kosovo was formed with its center in Pristina, and from 1888 in Skopje.⁴

of Skopje, Pristina, Prizren, Peja, New Bazaar and Taslixha⁵ The Sanjaks were divided into kaza (districts) where the Sanjak of Prizren was divided into three districts:

1. Prizren District with one nahija, 2. Tetovo District with 160 villages, 3. Luma District with 49 villages.⁶ The Ottoman-Austro-Hungarian War created great hardships for the population of Prizren and all of Kosovo. After burning Skopje, General Piccolomini conquered Prizren on November 6, 1689.⁷ After the occupation of Kosovo (1912) by Serbia and Montenegro, the administrative regulation, namely the administrative-territorial division, immediately began. According to the Serbian census of 1913/14, Kosovo was divided into three districts: where the territory of the present-day municipality of Prizren was part of the Prizren District (districts: Gorë, Podgur, Podrime, Sharr).⁸ After World War I, at the end of 1918, as is known, the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats and Slovenes, or Yugoslav, was created, which was destroyed in April 1941. Regarding the administrative-territorial division after the end of World War I, the territorial division into regions, districts and the organization of civil power in 1918 remained the same as in 1913. Kosovo was divided into three regions: Kosovo, Zvečan and Prizren.⁹ According to the new territorial division in 1920, the territory of Kosovo was divided into 5 regions: The Prizren Region was headquartered in Prizren with the districts of Gora (Vranishte), Luma (Bicaj), Podgur (Suhareka), Anadrina (Rahovec), Sharr (Prizren) and Has (Kruma). It should be noted that Luma and Has were part of Albania, but Serbia at this time had occupied them and considered them its own, like other Albanian areas in Kosovo, Macedonia and Montenegro.¹⁰ The Kingdom of the Serbs, Serb-Macedonians, according to the Constitution of Vidovdan, was divided into 33 provinces. According to the Decree-Law of 22 April 1922, the territory of Kosovo was divided into parts of these provinces: where the present-day municipality of Prizren was called the Sharr district, it was part of the Kosovo Province.¹¹ This administrative and territorial division remained until January 6, 1929, when the January monarcho-fascist dictatorship was established. Then the Kingdom changed its name to the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, while its territory was divided into new administrative-territorial units – into banovinas, headed by bani. This division was made by the Law of 3.X.1929.

² Hazim Šabanović, H. (1952) Administrative Division of the Yugoslav Lands under Ottoman Rule until the Peace of Karlowitz (1699), *Yearbook of the Historical Society of Bosnia and Herzegovina*, Sarajevo. p. 177.

³ Rizaj, S. (1968) Mining in Kosovo and Neighboring Regions from the 15th to the 17th Century, Prishtina. p. 7-19.

⁴ Osmani, J & Manaj, R. (2014) Administrative-Territorial Division of Kosovo 1944–2010, Academy of Sciences and Arts of Kosovo (ASHAK), Prishtina. p. 16.

⁵ Gersina, Macedonia and the Turkish Conquest, Belgrade, 1903. p. 35

⁶ Rahimi, Sh. (1969) The Vilayets of Kosovo, Institute of Textbooks and Teaching Aids of the Autonomous Socialist Province of Kosovo, Prishtina. p. 16.

⁷ Kosovo then and now, February 1973, p. 923.

⁸ Rečnik Mesta u oslobođenoj oblasti Stare Srbije, we are serving data, Belgrade, 1914.

⁹ Rushiti, L. (1981) The Kaçak Movement in Kosovo 1918–1928, Prishtina. p. 15

¹⁰ Almanac Kraljevine SHS, 1921, Belgrade, 1922, pg. 123-126.

¹¹ Kraljevine SHS News Service, no. 9/28.IV.1922.

The entire state was divided into 9 banovinas. The territory of the banovinas between which Kosovo was divided, according to the Law on the name and division of the Kingdom into administrative units¹² was divided into districts: The Sharr District, which included the territory of the present-day municipality of Prizren, was within the framework of the Vardar Banovina. With the beginning of World War II and the arrival of German, Italian and Bulgarian troops, Kosovo was divided into three occupation zones: the German, Italian and Bulgarian zones, which established their own administration.

On 8 February 1945, the Supreme Staff of the UNÇJ, signed by Tito, issued an Order establishing Military Administration in Kosovo.¹³ The administrative regulation of Kosovo after the Second World War was carried out by the People's Republic of Serbia, because this territory, without the will of the people, arbitrarily entered the framework of Serbia. In Kosovo, all the powers for the administrative regulation of territorial division were in the People's Republic of Serbia, therefore all sources regarding the division and administrative regulation of the territory of Kosovo lead us to the legal acts of the People's Republic of Serbia in this sphere of activity.¹⁴ On August 7, 1945, the Anti-Fascist Council of the People's Liberation Assembly of Yugoslavia approved the Resolution of the Provincial Assembly of the Autonomous Province of Kosovo and Metohija.¹⁵ The Presidency of the People's Assembly of Serbia, based on the decision of the Provisional People's Assembly of Yugoslavia, passed the Law on the Establishment and Regulation of the KPA. With this Law, Kosovo was divided into 15 districts, where the territory of the Prizren municipality was again part of the Sharr district.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1 Prizren settlements in the administrative-territorial unit during 1947 Prizren

The People's Republic of Serbia, in comparison with other republics, had two autonomous provinces in its composition. It adopted laws that determined that Serbia as a federal unit consists of the regions and the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina and the Autonomous Province of Kosovo and Metohija.¹⁶ according to an archival document dated 17 June 1947 - Regulations for the budgeting of revenues and donations of the People's Council of the Krahinor of the Autonomous Regions of Kosovo and Metohisa. The district of Prizren also existed in Kosovo.¹⁷ Until 1947, Prizren was the seat of Kosovo, when this function was transferred to Pristina.¹⁸ The city of Prizren has many advantages, primarily in terms of natural and environmental character, etc. As can be seen, Mamush was the KPV (People's Council of the Regions) with headquarters in Mamuah, with the settlements of Mamush and Medvec¹⁹ in the Suhareka district.

¹² Newspaper Service KJ, no. 323/4.X.1929.

¹³ Nosi,L. (1994). The Re-occupation of Kosovo, September 1944 – July 1945, Tirana. p. 161.

¹⁴ Lipa, S. (1982). Kosovo in the Period of Reconstruction, Institute of the History of Kosovo, Prishtina, 1982p. 44.

¹⁵ Law on the establishment and organization of the Autonomous Kosovo-Metohija Region, "Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", no. 28/45.

¹⁶ Law on the Establishment and Organization of the Autonomous Kosovo-Metohija Oblast, "Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", no. 28/45.

¹⁷ ASK, Fund: Provincial People's Council, Prizren, Box 1, year 1945-1946.

¹⁸ Kosovo then and now, February 1973, p.937.

¹⁹ Osmani,J & Manaj, R. (2014) Administrative–Territorial Division of Kosovo 1944–2010, Academy of Sciences and Arts of Kosovo (ASHAK), Prishtina.p. 105.

Map 1. Administrative-territorial division of the Prizren District into 10 KPV in 1947

With the Law on the Administrative Division of the Republic of Serbia on 18 April 1947²⁰ It is defined as follows: administrative-territorial administrative-territorial are: *çiçket, çiçdet, razonet e çiçteve.*

Table 1. Places (towns, villages, neighborhoods, workers' neighborhoods and other settlements) in the composition of the People's Councils of the places

Nr.r	PPC	HEADQUARTERS	Places (towns, villages, neighborhoods, workers' neighborhoods and other settlements) in the composition of the KPV
1	Krushë e Madhe	Krushë e Madhe ²¹	Krushë e Madhe, Krushë e Vogël, Randobravë, Celinë.
2	Sërbicë e Epërme	Sërbicë e Epërme	Velezhë, Gilanc ²² , Sërbicë e Epërme, Sërbicë e Poshtme, Zojz, Novak, Piranë, Smaç, Trepetnicë, Caparc, Shpinadi.
3	Dushanovë	Dushanovë	Atmaxhë, Grazhdanik, Dushanovë, Landovicë, Nashec, Petrovosellë, Tupec.
4	Zhur	Zhur	Vllashnje, Vërrnicë, Dobrushtë, Zhur, Kobajë, Shkozë.
5	Zym	Zym	Dedaj, Gjonaj, Zym, Kabash, Krajk, Luki, Karashëngjergj, Lubizhdë, Romajë.
6	Lubizhdë	Lubizhdë	Vërbiçan, Gërncar, Dojnicë, Kabash, Korishë, Lubizhdë, Lutogllavë, Novosellë, Skorobisht.

²⁰ Official Gazette of the NRS, no. April 17/24, 1947

²¹ The settlements of Krushë e Madhe and Celinë are today located within the municipality of Rahovec.

²² The settlement of Gilanca is separated from the composition of the KPV in Lower Srbica and attached to the composition of the KPV in Sopi, Suhareka district. According to the Decree on administrative-territorial changes in the territory of the People's Republic of Serbia No. 5009, Belgrade, October 6, 1949

7	Plane	Plane	Gorozhup, Kojushë, Mazrek, Milaj, Plane.
8	Reçan	Reçan	Zhivinjan, Jabllanicë, Llokvicë, Manastirc, Nebregoshte, Reçan, Struzhje.
9	Sreckë	Sreckë	Lubinje e Ep., Gornjesello, Lubinje e P., Drajçiq, Mushnikovë, Pllanjan, Sreckë.
10	Hoçë e Qytetit	Hoçë e Qytetit	Bilushë, Jeshkovë, Kushnin, Leskovec, Lez, Lybiçevë, Poslishtë, Hoçë e Qytetit.

This Law abolished districts as administrative-territorial units, so that republican bodies are directly linked to the districts.

2.2. Settlements of the municipality of Prizren during 1953 divided into communes and cities

The People's Assembly of the RFPJ adopted on 10.4.1952 the General Law on People's Councils, which designated the councils as local bodies of state power and bodies of popular government in communes, districts and cities²³

Map 2. Territorial-administrative division of Prizren in 1953

Based on the Federal Law on People's Councils of 1952 and the Law on the Administrative-Territorial Division of the Republic of Serbia,²⁴ The territory of Serbia is divided into municipalities, districts and cities. This division was made on the basis of the competencies of the Republic of Serbia, with the Decree of the Presidium of the RP of Serbia of April 22, 1952 regarding the decision on the decentralization of the economic and administrative apparatus.

²³ Official Gazette of the FNRJ no. 33/19.04.1952.

²⁴ NRS official gazette, No. 15/1952.

Table 2. Division into municipalities, districts and cities.

<i>Nr.r</i>	<i>Municipality City</i>	– SETTLEMENTS
1	Prizreni	Prizreni
2	Krushë e Madhe	Krushë e Madhe, Krushë e Vogël, Randobravë, Celinë.
3	Sërbicë e Epërme	Velezhë, Sërbicë e Epërme, Sërbicë e Poshtme, Zojz, Novak, Piranë, Smaç, Trepeticë, Caparc, Shpinadi.
4	Dushanovë	Atmaxhë, Grazhdanik, Dushanovë, Landovicë, Nashec, Petrovosellë, Tupec.
5	Zhur	Vllashnje, Vërrnicë, Dobrushtë, Zhur, Kobajë, Shkozë.
6	Zym	Dedaj, Gjonaj, Zym, Kabash, Krajk, Luki, Karashëngjergj, Lubizhdë, Romajë.
7	Lubizhdë	Vërbiçan, Gërçar, Dojnicë, Kabash, Korishë, Lubizhdë, Lutogllavë, Novosellë, Skorobisht.
8	Plane	Gorozhup, Kojushë, Mazrek, Milaj, Plane.
9	Reçan	Zhivinjan, Jabllanicë, Llokvicë, Manastirc, Nebregoshte, Reçan, Struzhje.
10	Sreckë	Lubinje e Ep., Gornjesello, Lubinje e P., Drajçiq, Mushnikovë, Pllanjan, Sreckë.
11	Hoçë e Qytetit	Bilushë, Jeshkovë, Kushnin, Leskovec, Lez, Lybiçevë, Poslishtë, Hoçë e Qytetit.

The change in the role of the people's councils of cities and municipalities was determined by the Law on People's Councils and the Law on People's Councils of Cities and Municipalities, which was approved by the Serbian Parliament on 8.9.1952.²⁵ With this Decree, with the Law of September 20, 1952, the foreseen division was completed. The territory of Kosovo is divided into these districts: the territory of the municipality of Prizren was part of the Sharr District which included: Dushanova, Upper Serbica, Hoça e Qytetit, Lubizhda, Planeja, Prizreni, Reçan, Sredcka, Krusha e Madhe, Zymi and Zhuri. While Mamusha was in the Suhareka district even at this time as a separate KPV with headquarters in Mamushë with settlements Mamushen and Medveci²⁶ Based on the General Law on the Regulation of Municipalities and Districts, which the Federal Assembly approved on 16.6.1955²⁷ further decentralization of popular power began.

2.3. Prizren District in the People's Councils of Municipalities in 1955

The most important change was the introduction of municipal regulation. Based on this general law, the People's Assembly of the RS adopted the Law on the Territories of Districts and Municipalities in the Republic of Serbia on 11 July 1955.²⁸ According to this Law, the districts of Gora, Podrimë and Suhareka, which are attached to the Prizren Regional Administrative District, which was previously called Sharr.

²⁵ NRS official gazette, issue 15/1952.

²⁶ Osmani, J & Manaj, R. (2014) Administrative–Territorial Division of Kosovo 1944–2010, Academy of Sciences and Arts of Kosovo (ASHAK), Prishtina, p. 141.

²⁷ Official Gazette of the FNRJ, no. 16/22.06.1955.

²⁸ Official Gazette of the NRS, no. 56/20.07.1955.

Table 3. Prizren District with the local people's councils

Nr	City – Municipality	SETTLEMENTS
1	Banja	Banja, Bellanica, Guriqi, Dragobili, Jançishta, Joviqi, Kravasaria, Lladroviqi, Lladrovci, Maxhara, Malisheva, Maralia, Milanoviqi, Mirusha, Astrazubi, Pagarusha, Seniku, Caravrana.
2	Bellobrad	Bellobrada, Blaqi, Brezna, Brodosani, Brruti, Buzezi, Buçja, Zaplluxha, Zgatari, Zymi, Kapra, Kosava, Kuklibegu, Kuki, Plava, Pllajniku dhe Rrenci.
3	Krusha e Madhe	Krusha e Madhe, Zojzi, Xërxa, Krusha e Vog. Mamusha, Medveci, Nagavci, Pirana, Randobrava, Celina.
4	Vlashnja	Bilusha, Vlashnja, Vërmica, Dobrushta, Shkoza, Grazhdaniku, Zhuri, Murademi, Jeshkova, Kushtendili ²⁹ , Kobaja, Lezi, Lybiçeva, Nasheci, Poslishta, Hoça e Qytetit
5	Dragashi	Baçka, Brodi, Vranishta, Dikanca, Dragashi, Xërxa, Kërstaci, Kukulani, Leshtani, Lubovishta, Mlika, Orçusha, Radesha, Rapça dhe Shajna
6	Dulja	Bllaca, Grejçevci, Guncati, Dulja, Javori, Kostërci, Lluzhnica, Nishori, Tumeçina, Çadraku.
7	Gjinaj	Gorozhupi, Gjonaj, Zymi, Krajku, Karashëngjergji, Kojusha, Mazreku, Milaj, Planeja, Tupeci.
8	Krusheva	Gllloboçica, Zlipotoku, Krusheva, Restelica.
9	Rahoveci	Bellacerkva, Brestovci, Bërnjaça, Hoça e Madhe, Potoçani i Epërm, Potoçani i Poshtëm, Drenovci, Zatriqi, Zoçishta, Kozniku, Hoça e Vogël, Nushpala, Apterusha, Rahoveci, Pastasela, Retia, Sanovci dhe Sopniqi.
10	Prizreni	Atmaxha, Velezha, Vërbiçani, Sërbica e Epërme, Gërñçari, Dojnica, Sërbica e Poshtme, Dushanova, Jabllanica, Kabashi, Korisha, Landovica, Leskoveci, Lubizhda, Lutogllava, Shumadia e Re, Novosella, Novaku, Prizreni, Petrovasella, Skorobishti, Smaçi, Trepetnica, Caparci, Shpinadia.
11	Ratkovci	Bratotini, Bërnjaka, Gexha, Denja, Dobërdoli, Llapçeva, Mrasori, Petkoviqi, Polluzha, Radosta, Ratkovci, Kramoviku, Çifllaku Saroshi.
12	Rogova	Gërçina, Damjani, Dedaj, Kabashi i Hasit, Kushnini, Lukinaj, Lubizhda e Hasit, Rogova, Romaja.
13	Srecka	Gornja Lubinja, Gornjasella, Lubinja e Poshtme, Drajçiqi, Zhiviniani, Llokvica, Manastirica, Mushnikova, Nepregoshti, Pllanjani, Reçani, Sredska, Stuzhja.
14	Suhareka	Budakova, Bukoshi, Vraniqi, Vërshevci, Gilanca, Grejkovci, Dvorani, Dellovci, Dobërdolani, Dubrava, Gjinovci, Krushica, Leshani, Maçiteva, Mohlani, Mushitishta, Neprebishta, Papazi, Peçani, Popovlani, Rashtani, Reçani, Savrova, Samadrazha, Sellograzhda, Semetishti, Sllapuzhani, Sopia, Stravuçina, Studenica, Suhareka, Topliçani, Tërni.

²⁹ In the Prizren district: the settlement of Kushtendil (K.K. Kushtendil) is separated from the composition of the municipality of Vlashnja and is attached to the municipality of Prizren according to the Decree on the promulgation of the law on amendments and supplements to the law on the territories of districts and municipalities in the People's Republic of Serbia No. 915 in Belgrade, December 21, 19560

Map 3. Territorial-administrative division of Prizren in 1955

2.4. Prizren District with People's Councils of Municipalities in 1957

Based on the Law on Amendments and Supplements to the Law on the Territory of Districts and Municipalities in the Republic of Serbia, approved by the People's Assembly of the People's Republic of Serbia, at the meeting of the House of Republics held on 10 June 1957, the territory of Kosovo was divided into districts and municipalities within the districts.³⁰ The Prizren District also participated with the People's Councils of the municipalities: Banja, Belobrada, Krusha e Madhe, Vlashnja, Dragash, Prizreni, Ratkovci, Rogova, Srecka and Suhareka.

³⁰ Official gazette of NRS no. 27/22 June 1957

Table 4. Prizren District with the People's Councils of the municipalities: Banja, Belobrada, Krusha e Madhe, Vlashnja, Dragash, Prizren, Ratkovci, Rogova, Srecka and Suhareka.

Nr	City – Municipality	SETTLEMENTS
1	Banja	Banja, Bellanica, Guriqi, Dragobili, Jançishta, Joviqi, Kravasaria, Lladroviqi, Lladrovci, Maxhara, Malisheva, Maralia, Milanoviqi, Mirusha, Astrazubi, Pagarusha, Seniku, Caravrana.
2	Bellobrad	Bellobrada, Blaqi, Brezna, Brodosani, Brruti, Buzezi, Buçja, Zaplluxha, Zgatari, Zymi, Kapra, Kosava, Kuklibegu, Kuki, Plava, Pllajniku dhe Rrenci.
3	Krusha e Madhe	Krusha e Madhe, Zojzi, Xerxa, Krusha e Vog. Mamusha, Medveci, Nagavci, Pirana, Randobrava, Celina.
4	Vlashnja	Bilusha, Vlashnja, Vërmica, Dobrushta, Shkoza, Grazhdaniku, Zhuri, Murademi, Jeshkova, Kushtendili ³¹ , Kobaja, Lezi, Lybiçeva, Nasheci, Poslishta, Hoça e Qytetit
5	Dragashi	Baçka, Brodi, Vranishta, Dikanca, Dragashi, Xërxa, Kërstaci, Kukulani, Leshani, Lubovishta, Mlika, Orçusha, Radesha, Rapça dhe Shajna
6	Prizreni	Atmaxha, Velezha, Vërbiçani, Sërbica e Epërme, Gërñçari, Dojnica, Sërbica e Poshtme, Dushanova, Jabllanica, Kabashi, Korisha, Landovica, Leskoveci, Lubizhda, Lutogllava, Shumadia e Re, Novosella, Novaku, Prizreni, Petrovasella, Skorobishti, Smaçi, Trepetnica, Caparci, Shpinadia.
7	Ratkovci	Bratotini, Bërrnjaka, Gexha, Denja, Dobërdoli, Llapçeva, Mrasori, Petkoviqi, Polluzha, Radosta, Ratkovci, Kramoviku, Çifllaku Saroshi.
8	Rogova	Gërçina, Damjani, Dedaj, Kabashi i Hasit, Kushnini, Lukinaj, Lubizhda e Hasit, Rogova, Romaja.
9	Srecka	Gornja Lubinja, Gornjasella, Lubinja e Poshtme, Drajçiqi, Zhivinjani, Llokvica, Manastirica, Mushnikova, Nepregoshti, Pllanjani, Reçani, Sredska, Stuzhja.
10	Suhareka	Budakova, Bukoshi, Vraniqi, Vërshevc, Gilanca, Grejkovci, Dvorani, Dellovci, Dobërdolani, Dubrava, Gjinovci, Krushica, Leshani, Maçiteva, Mohlani, Mushitishta, Neprebishta, Papazi, Peçani, Popovlani, Rashtani, Reçani, Savrova, Samadrazha, Sellograzhda, Semetishti, Sllapuzhani, Sopia, Stravuçina, Studenica, Suhareka, Topliçani, Tërni.

As can be seen from the table, the cities and municipalities of Dulja, Gjonaj, Krusheva, and Rahovec are being removed.

³¹ In the Prizren district: the settlement of Kushtendil (K.K. Kushtendil) is separated from the composition of the municipality of Vlashnja and is attached to the municipality of Prizren according to the Decree on the promulgation of the law on amendments and supplements to the law on the territories of districts and municipalities in the People's Republic of Serbia No. 915 in Belgrade, December 21, 1956

2.5. Settlements in the Municipality of Prizren in 1959

The Law on the Territories of Municipalities and Districts in the Republic of Serbia in 1959³² determined that only municipalities would exist in Kosovo. According to the Law on the Territories of Municipalities and Districts in the Republic of Serbia of 1959, the following municipalities exist in Kosovo: Deçan, Dragash, Gjakova, Gnjilane, Ferizaj, Prishtina, Peja, Mitrovica, Kamenica, Viti, Podujevo, Suhareka, Rahovec, Vushtrri, Istog, Klina, Kaçanik, Shtërpçë, Zym³³, Zubin Potok, Lipjan, Skënderaj, Glllogovc, Malisheva, Leposaviq, Novobërdë, Prizren and Orllani. Thus, from 1960 to 1965, there were 28 municipalities³⁴ in Kosovo.

According to this law, there will be 60 settlements in the municipality of Prizren, but the following settlements will be missing: Pousk in the Zhupa region and the settlements of Has.

Map No. 4. Prizren and Zym divided in 1960-1965

³² NRS official gazette, no. 51/1959.

³³ The municipality of Zym is attached to the municipality of Prizren, which from 1960 to 1965 was a separate municipality.

³⁴ Osmani, J & Manaj, R. (2014) Administrative-Territorial Division of Kosovo 1944-2010, Academy of Sciences and Arts of Kosovo (ASHAK), Prishtina, p.42.

Table 5. The settlements of the municipality of Prizren without the settlements of Has, which during these years was a municipality in itself like the municipality of Zym.

1. Atmaxha	21. Murademi	41. Krusha e Vogël
2. Billusha	22. Zojzi	42. Novaka
3. Velezha	23. Jabllanica	43. Novosella
4. Vërbiçani	24. Jeshkova	44. Nebërgoshti
5. Vlashnja	25. Kabashi	45. Nasheci
6. Vërmica	26. Korisha	46. Petrovasella
7. Dobrushta	27. Kushtendili	47. Prizreni
8. Shkoza	28. Kobaja	48. Pllanjani
9. Sërbica e Epërme	29. Landovica	49. Poslishta
10. Gërçari	30. Leskoveci	50. Pirana
11. Lubinja e Epërme	31. Llokvica	51. Randobrava
12. Gonjasella	32. Lezi	52. Reçani
13. Grazhdaniku	33. Lubizhda	53. Skorobishta
14. Dojnica	34. Lutogllava	54. Smaçi
15. Sërbica e Poshtme	35. Shumadia e Re ³⁵	55. Srecka
16. Dushanova	36. Lubiçeva	56. Struzhja
17. Lubinja e Poshtme	37. Manastirci	57. Trepetnica
18. Draçiqi	38. Mushnikova	58. Hoça e Qytetit
19. Zhivinjan	39. Mamusha ³⁶	59. Caparci
20. Zhuri	40. Medveci	60. Shpinadia

The municipality of Zymi is attached to the municipality of Prizren, which from 1960 to 1965 was a separate municipality with these 19 settlements: Gërçina, Gorozhupi, Damjani, Dedaj, Gjonaj, Zymi, Karashëngjergji, Krajku, Kojusha, Kabashi i Hasit, Kushnini, Lukinaj, Lubizhda e Hasit, Mazreku, Milaj, Planeja, Rogova, Romaja, Tupec.

2.6. Settlements of the Municipality of Prizren after 1975

After the 1974 Constitution, Kosovo made the first territorial organization of the country. The Assembly of the Autonomous Socialist Province of Kosovo, in the meeting held on July 15, 1975, adopted the Law on the Territorial Organization of Kosovo. Based on this Law, 22 municipalities with 1,431³⁷ settlements were formed, such as the municipalities of: Vitia, Vushtrri, Glllogovc, Gjilan, Deçan, Dragash, Gjakova, Istog, Kaçanik, Klina, Kamenica, Mitrovica, Leposoviqi, Lipjan, Rahovec, Peja, Podujevo, Prizren, Prishtina, Skenderaj, Suhareka and Ferizaj.

Municipality of Prizren – Settlements

1. Atmaxhe 2. Billushe 3. Velezhe 4. Vlashne 5. Vërbiçan 6. Vërmicë 7. Lubinje e Epërme 8. Gornjeselle 9. Sërbicë e Epërme 10. Gorozhup 11. Gërçar 12. Grazhdanik 13. Dedaj 14. Dobrushtë 15. Lubunje e Poshtme 16. Srbica e Poshtme 17. Donjicë 18. Draçiq 19. Dushanovë 20. Gjonaj 21. Zhivinjan 22. Zhur 23. Zojz 24. Zym 25. Jabllanicë 26. Jeshkovë 27. Kabash 28. Kabash i Hasit 29. Karashëngjergj 30. Kobajë 31. Kojushë 32. Korishë 33. Krajk 34. Kushtendil

³⁵ This settlement is today known as Malësia e Re.

³⁶ Today it is a municipality in its own right.

³⁷ KK no.015-1, Pristina, July 15, 1975; Official Gazette of the Autonomous Socialist Province of Kosovo, no.25/ July 29, 1975.

35. Kushnin 36. Landovicë 37. Lokvicë 38. Lez 39. Leskovec 40. Lukinaj 41. Lubizhde 42. Lubiçevë 43. Lubizhde of Has 44. Lutogllavë 45. Mamushë 46. Krushë e Vogël 47. Manastirë 48. Mazrek 49. Medvec 50. Milaj 51. Muradem 52. Mushnikovë 53. Nashec 54. Nepregoshë 55. Novoselë 56. Novak 57. Shumadi e Re 58. Petrovosella 59. Piranë 60. Planjan 61. Planejë62. Poslishtë 63. Pouskë 64. Prizren 65. Randobravë 66. Reçan 67. Romajë 68. Skorobishtë 69. Smaç70. Sredskë 71. Struzhë 72. Trepetnicë 73. Tupec 74. Hoçë e Qytetit 75. Caparc 76. Shkozë77. Shpenad.

Map No. 5 Settlements of the Municipality of Prizren after 1975

After the end of the war and the liberation of Kosovo, in the first years there was no specific administrative-territorial division. The organization that existed before the acquisition of autonomy was implemented, with the exception of the Municipality of Zveçan.³⁸

According to Regulation No. 2000/43 of 27 July 2000 on the number, names and borders of municipalities, the municipality of Prizren had 73 settlements:

1. Atmaxhe, 2. Bilushe 3. Caparc, 4. Dedaj, 5. Gjonaj 6. Dojnice 7. Srbica e Ultë 8. Lubinja e Ultë 9. Drajçiq 10. Dushanovë 11. Srbica e Epërme 12. Lubinja e Epërme 13. Gorjnasellë 14. Gorozhub 15. Grazhdenik 16. Grançar 17. Hoça e Qytetit 18. Jabllanicë 19. Jeshkovë 20. Kabash 21. Kabash i Hasit 22. Karashengjergj 23. Kobaje 24. Kojushe 25. Korishe 26. Krajk 27. Kushnin 28. Kushtendil 29. Landovicë 30. Leskovec 31. Lez 32. Lybiçevë 33. Lubizhdë 34. Lubizhdë e H. I 35. Lubizhdë e H. II 36. Lukinja 37. Lutogllavë 38. Llokvicë 39. Krusha e Vogël 40. Mamushë 41. Manastiriçë 42. Mazrek 43. Medvec 44. Milaj 45. Mushnikovë 46. Nashec 47. Nebregosht 48. Novak 49. Novoselë 50

³⁸ Osmani, J & Manaj, R. (2014) Administrative-Territorial Division of Kosovo 1944-2010, Academy of Sciences and Arts of Kosovo (ASHAK), Prishtina. p.55.

Petrovosella 51 Piranë 52 Planejë 53 Pllanjan 54 Poslishtë 55 Prizren 56 Randobravë 57 Reçan 58 Romajë 59 Skorobisht 60 Smaç 61 Shpinad 62 Sreckë 63 Struzhë 64 Trepetincë 65 Tupec 66 Velezë 67 Vllashnjë 68 Vërbiçan 69 Vërnica 70 Zhivinjan 71 Zym 72 Zojz 73 Zhur

According to Administrative Order No. 2004/23 dated 16 April 2004, the municipality of Prizren had 77 settlements: 1. Atmaxhe 2. Billushe 3. Caparc 4. Dedaj 5. Dobrushte 6. Dojnice 7. Drajqiq 8. Dushanovë 9. Gërçar 10. Gjonaj 11. Gornjaselle 12. Gorozhup 13. Grazhdanik 14. Hoçë e Qytetit 15. Jabllanice 16. Jeshkovë 17. Kabash 18. Kabash i Hashit 19. Karashengjergj 20. Kobaje 21. Kojushe 22. Korishe 23. Krajk 24. Krushe e Vogel 25. Kushnin 26. Kushtendil 27. Landovicë 28. Leskovec 29. Lez 30. Llokvicë 31. Lubinjë e Epërme 32. Lubinjë e Poshtme 33. Lubiçevë 34. Lubizhdë 35. Lubizhdë e Hasit 36. Lukinaj 37. Lutogllavë 38. Malësi e Re 39. Mamushë³⁹ 40. Manastiricë 41. Mazrek 42. Medvec 43. Milaj 44. Muradem 45. Mushnikovë 46. Nashec 47. Nebregoshtë 48. Novak 49. Novoselle 50. Petrovë 51. Piranë 52. Pllanejë 53. Pllanjan 54. Poslishtë 55. Pouskë 56. Prizren 57. Randobravë 58. Reçan 59. Romajë 60. Srbica e Epërme 61. Srbica e Posht. 62. Shkozë 63. Shpinad 64. Skorobishtë 65. Smaç 66. Sredskë 67. Struzhë 68. Trepetnica 69. Tupec 70. Velezë 71. Vërbiçan 72. Vërmicë 73. Vlashnjë 74. Živinjan 75. Zhur 76. Zojz 77. Zym

With the entry into force of the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo and its approval by the Assembly of the Republic of Kosovo, the President of the Republic of Kosovo signed the Law on Municipal Boundaries on 15 June 2008. Article 5.5 of the Law on Administrative Boundaries of Municipalities determines the number of municipalities of the Republic of Kosovo, including the municipalities of Hani i Elezit, Junik and Mamusha. These three municipalities have been pilot municipal units for several years, and now they exercise full municipal powers and responsibilities based on the Law on Local Self-Government⁴⁰.

According to Law no. 03/L-040 on local self-government dated 20 February 2008, the municipality of Prizren had 72 settlements:

1. Atmaxhe 2. Billushe 3. Caparc 4. Dedaj 5. Gjonaj 6. Dojnice 7. Srbica e Poshtme 8. Lubinje e Poshtme 9. Drajqiq 10. Dushanovë 11. Srbica e Epërme 12. Lubinje e Epërme 13. Gornjaselle 14. Gorozhup 15. Grozhdanik 16. Gërçar 17. Hoçë e Qytetit 18. Jabllanicë 19. Jeshkovë 20. Kabash 21. Kabash i Hasit 22. Karashengjergj 23. Kobaje 24. Kojushe 25. Korishe 26. Krajk 27. Kushnin 28. Kushtendil 29. Landovicë 30. Leskovec 31. Lez 32. Lubiçevo 33. Lubizhdë 34. Lubizhdë of Has I 35. Lubizh. of Has II⁴¹ 36. Lukinaj 37. Lutogllavë 38. Llokvicë 39. Krushë e Vogël 40. Manastirica 41. Mazrek 42. Medvec 43. Milaj 44. Mushnikovë 45. Nashec 46. Nebregosht 47. Novak 48. Novoselle 49. Petrovë 50. Piranë 51. Pllanejë 52. Pllanjan 53. Poslishtë 54. Prizren 55. Randobravë 56. Reçan 57. Romajë 58. Skorobishtë 59. Smaç 60. Shpenadi 61. Sredskë 62. Struzhë 63. Trepetincë 64. Tupec 65. Velezë 66. Vlashnjë 67. Vërbiçan 68. Vërmicë 69. Zhivinjan 70. Zym 71. Zojz 72. Zhur

According to Law no. 03/L-040 on local self-government dated February 20, 2008, the following settlements were missing: 1. Dobrushti, 2. Muradem, 3. Pouska, 4. Shkozë, 5. Malësi e Re.

According to the 2024 Kosovo Population, Household and Housing Census, the population by gender, ethnicity and residence, the municipality of Prizren has 76 residences.⁴² 1. Atmaxhë 2. Billushë 3. Caparc 4. Dedaj 5. Gjonaj 6. Dojnicë 7. Sërbicë e Poshtme 8. Lubinjë e Poshtme 9. Drajqiq 10. Dushanovë 11. Sërbicë e Epërme 12. Lubinjë e Epërme 13. Gornjasellë 14. Gorozhup 15. Grozhdanik 16. Gërçar 17. Hoçë e Qytetit 18. Jabllanicë 19. Jeshkovë 20. Kabash 21. Kabash i Hasit 22. Karashëngjergj 23. Kobajë 24. Kojushë 25. Korishë 26. Krajk 27. Kushnin 28. Kushtendil 29. Landovicë 30. Leskovec 31. Lez 32. Lubiçevë 33. Lubizhdë 34. Lubizhdë e Hasit 35. Dobrushtë 36. Lukinaj 37. Lutogllavë 38. Llokvicë 39. Krushë e Vogël 40. Manastiricë 41. Mazrek 42. Medvec 43

³⁹ In 2008, Mamusha became a municipality in its own right.

⁴⁰ Ibid., p. 60

⁴¹ In the last population census in 2024, only one Lubizhda e Hasi was registered.

⁴² KAS, Population, Households and Housing Census in Kosovo 2024, Population by gender, ethnicity and place of residence Pristina, July 2025 p.33

Milaj 44 Mushnikovë 45 Nashec 46 Nebregosht 47 Novak 48 Novosellë 49 Petrovë 50 Piranë 51 Pllanëj 52 Pllanjan 53 Poslishtë 54 Prizren 55 Randobravë 56 Reçan 57 Romajë 58 Skorobishtë 59 Smaç 60 Shpenadi 61 Sredskë 62 Struzhë 63 Trepetincë 64 Tupec 65 Velezhë 66 Vlashnjë 67 Vërbiçan 68 Vërmicë 69 Zhivinjan 70 Zym 71 Zojz 72 Zhur 73 Muradem 74 Pouskë 75 Shkozë 76 Malesi e Re

Map No. 6. Prizren Municipality divided into 76 cadastral zones

CONCLUSIONS

After 1945, the territory of the municipality of Prizren has undergone changes in terms of territorial and administrative division, these changes stemming from the occupation of Kosovo by Serbia. The first change occurred through the adoption of the "Law on the Establishment and Regulation of the Autonomous Province of Kosovo and Metohija" where the first territorial changes occur to continue with some minor changes over the years until 1974, when Kosovo gained the status of a constituent element within the Yugoslav federation to continue with organizations and reorganizations until 2008. After the declaration of independence of Kosovo, legal provisions were adopted by the legitimate institutions of the Republic of Kosovo. The last legal provision regulating the administrative division of Kosovo, based on the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo, was adopted on June 15, 2008, as part of the Law on Administrative Borders of Municipalities where the municipality of Prizren has 76 cadastral zones

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